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SPEAKING AS A WAY OF IMPROVING LANGUAGE SKILLS

Speaking is considered as a crucial part of learning Russian as a foreign language. As a matter of fact, speaking is not merely about engaging students to repeat or memorize dialogues, but rather, they should be able to use the latter to communicate in real life situations. The way teachers should respond to the students thoughts and opinions is very important too, as the student should not be forced to speak under stress out of fear of failing. In such case, teachers need to set up such working environment and situations where students would hold useful and meaningful tasks that will eventually help them improving their speaking skills.

This can be realized – with the help of Task-Based approach, where students are prompted to work in groups with their classmates to complete a specific task. Task-Based approach allows learning to be maintained, and developed through performing a series of activities as a step towards successful task realization.

Among the four language skills (Reading, Writing, Speaking and Listening) Students consider speaking the Russian language as the most challenging and difficult one since it requires great “courage” as well as psychological preparation to produce the language. Speaking about psychology, students personalities play a huge role in determining how fast and accurately they will acquire this skill.

Those who are unafraid of making mistakes will generally be more talkative and thus, faster in learning. On the other hand, the conservative, and shy students may take a long time to learn speaking confidently, but when they do, they will make fewer errors and be proud of their newly acquired language skills. Learners might think in this case, which one is better? To talk too much while committing lots of mistakes or to think twice for better results. The answer to such question could be found by determining the aim of speaking in the first place – that is to build meaningful communication. In this case, to encourage learners to talk as much as possible to convey the communication message is much more important than thinking about the grammar rules before communicating. This would eventually lead to a fast learning process, even without realizing how many errors they’ve made.

Speaking tasks tend to be helpful as they are “Rehearsal”: When students have free discussions inside the classroom, they would eventually rehearse that outside. “Feedback”: Getting engaged in a speaking task which requires the use of all the

skills they have learned in previous lessons would provide feedback from both the teacher and students. “Engagement”: The completion of a speaking task can be really motivating and give real satisfaction. This would also encourage learners to practice more and more outside of the classroom as they gain more confidence in themselves. Speaking of motivation, students find themselves sometimes not motivated to talk due to the fact that they feel they lack involvement in the topics. Besides, they also need to overcome some psychological constraints before they are prepared to speak the language. Some students feel uneasy to talk in the classroom simply because there is always an audience in front of him, and so they would feel anxious out of fear of making fool of themselves.

Using Task-Based approach in this case, would enhance students self-confidence as they get the same opportunity to experience the learning process by putting the students in a situation in which they can decide on their own. It is worth noting though, that the implementation of such approach in a speaking class can lead to some students dominating the opportunity of talking over others.

References:

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This article describes the implementation of Task-Based approach to improve speaking skills in learning Russian as a foreign language.

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